

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D5.1 RO Model Adapted to EOSC

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Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
EVEREST	European Virtual Environment for Research Earth Science Themes
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reproducible
RELIANCE	Research Lifecycle Management technologies for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC
RO	Research Objects

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the main design decisions and the first implementation of the vocabulary specification that will be used in RELIANCE for the representation of the Research Objects (ROs) supported by the project. This specification (henceforth RELIANCE-RO) will evolve as the project continues its execution, taking into account the updates on reused resources that may happen in the meantime (in the RO-Crate community, in OpenAIRE, and in the Earth-Science-related research communities that are supported by this project).

One of the key characteristics of the proposed RO specification is that it is data-cube centric, as a fundamental differentiating principle of the Earth Science communities that are supported by RELIANCE.

Finally, RELIANCE-RO will be the basis for the implementation of the RELIANCE RO repository (ROHub), and hence compatibility is also looked for during its implementation.

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope

This deliverable presents the RELIANCE-RO specification, which will be used in RELIANCE for the representation of the Research Objects (ROs) that will be created, evolved and archived by the Earth Science research communities supported by the project (including those communities that are already present in the project, and also those engaged via the Open Call).

The RELIANCE-RO specification will be supported by the RELIANCE's upgraded ROHub repository (which will extend the current ROHub [5]). This repository will be one of the main services generated in RELIANCE that will be integrated in EOSC and made available via the EOSC portal and marketplace. Additionally, following the latest trends and efforts within the Research Object community, the RELIANCE-RO specification will be implemented as an RO-Crate application profile, as will be described in Section 4.

This deliverable has a strong relationship and dependency with two other deliverables from the project: D4.1, which proposes a metadata model for the representation of data cubes, an essential component of most of our Research Objects (as discussed in section 4), and D3.1, which identifies many of the semantic resources that will be used for the semantic enrichment of the RO textual components. RELIANCE Research Objects will allow incorporating the types of research artefacts that are normally handled by researchers in the domains of the project throughout the lifecycle of their research, as well as using semantic annotations that are in accordance with the metadata models and semantic resources that are identified in the aforementioned deliverables.

RELIANCE will also leverage and reuse other EOSC services for research data management, including services for depositing and sharing (B2DROP, B2SHARE, Zenodo), discovery and reuse (OpenAIRE Research Graph), and data management (Argos), as described in detail in Deliverable D6.1. RELIANCE will act as a bridge between other EOSC services, e.g., connecting data used by researchers, including Data Cubes for accessing Copernicus data and other data resources deposited in EOSC services (e.g., B2DROP, B2SHARE), the methods used to process such data (e.g., via EOSC Notebooks), and the final results published via scholarly communication services (e.g., Zenodo). Moreover, as part of the RO evolution, different snapshots/releases can be generated throughout the research lifecycle, so that they can be shared and published via research data platforms like B2SHARE and Zenodo for their long-term preservation and citation.

1.2 Audience

The main audience of this deliverable is the set of members of the RELIANCE Consortium, since this deliverable defines the representation needs for the description of Research Objects. The deliverable will be also useful for other EOSC related projects, since it will provide valuable input on how Research Objects for Earth Science related communities can be represented. It also addresses those communities and projects that are already adopting this approach. such as the RO-Crate community or the projects funded under the future HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-05 call, which explicitly calls for Research Object support. Finally, the deliverable is also relevant for developers of tools and services that may leverage or create Research Objects.

1.3 Structure

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 provides a summary of the specifications and metadata models that have been proposed for the representation of Research Objects, including the Wf4Ever RO specification, the EVER-EST RO extensions to the Wf4Ever RO specification, and the most recent RO-Crate.
- Section 3 describes metadata models that are relevant for RELIANCE, including a summary of the content from deliverables D4.1 and D3.1, and a discussion on available software description metadata models.
- Section 4 describes the RELIANCE-RO specification for the description of data-cube-centric ROs that provide support to Earth Science research communities. This RO specification is proposed as an extension (and application profile) of the ongoing RO-Crate.
- Section 5 finishes with the conclusions and next steps in the development and support of ROs for the RELIANCE community.

2. Relevant specifications for the representation of Research Objects

In this section we describe the specifications that have been used in the literature to represent Research Objects (ROs) [1]. ROs were coined as an abstraction to allow packaging and preserving the scientific resources of an investigation under a single aggregation. ROs aim at providing support to the general objective of facilitating scientific reproducibility and reuse of investigations made by researchers. This is possible, in principle, if all those materials that are relevant in the context of such experiments are included in these aggregations and hence shared with others.

The types of digital objects that may be included in a Research Object include, among others:

- Publications (and other types of documents, such as presentations, blog posts, etc.) that are derived from the described research, and which may be identified by their Digital Object Identifiers, for instance.
- Data used for the experiments (either as a copy or by means of a reference – e.g., a data DOI, descriptions of calls to an API, etc.).
- Software (including source code in a programming language, scripts, scientific workflow specifications, etc.) used to run the experiments, process data, generate and validate outputs, etc.
- Provenance information resulting from the execution of the software over some infrastructure, including the configuration settings used for such infrastructure.
- Infrastructure details, in the form of configuration settings, deployment instructions, virtual machines, containers, etc.
- Researchers involved in the experiments (e.g., identified by their ORCIDiDs), with their corresponding roles.
- Any number of annotations or groups of annotations around the whole experiment or parts of it, or about the research artefacts included in the Research Object.

Since its inception over 10 years ago [1], several RO specifications (and their corresponding management infrastructure, services and tools) have been proposed in the state of the art¹. We will provide details on the three most relevant specifications from the point of view of our focus in RELIANCE: The Wf4Ever RO specification (now deprecated), the EVER-EST RO extension and the ongoing RO-Crate specification.

¹ Most of them are listed at <https://www.researchobject.org/scopes/>

2.1 The Wf4Ever RO Specification

One of the first implementations of the RO concept was done in the context of the EU Wf4Ever project (<http://wf4ever.org/>), where several ontologies were designed and implemented to describe ROs, the scientific workflows that they contained and the provenance of their executions. In the context of this project, some management infrastructure for the creation, maintenance and archival of ROs was also created.

The main focus of the Wf4Ever project was the preservation of workflow-centric Research Objects, understood as the representation of research where scientific workflows were key in the development of the experiments. Hence the Wf4Ever RO specification was quite extensive in terms of the representation of this specific type of research artefact. The following ontologies were created to describe these types of ROs and their aggregated research artefacts:

- RO model: <http://purl.org/wf4ever/ro#>
- RO evolution model: <https://w3id.org/ro/roevo>
- Wfdesc model (for the description of scientific workflows): <https://w3id.org/ro/wfdesc>
- Wfprov model (for the description of workflow execution provenance): <https://w3id.org/ro/wfprov>
- RO terms, for the description of typical terms used in annotations of resources (e.g., hypothesis, exampleValue, technicalContact, etc.): <https://w3id.org/ro/2016-01-28/roterms>
- Wf4Ever ontology, for the description of some specific types of workflows, and their parts, commonly found in these ROs: <https://w3id.org/ro/wf4ever>

A general overview of the Wf4Ever RO specification (also described in detail in [2]) is provided in Figures 1 and 2. Figure 1 shows an overview of the model through an example: several resources (some of which may be workflows) are aggregated in an RO. The RO has a Manifest (which contains all the necessary metadata and organizational structure of the RO), and for which there are annotations, following the Open Annotation vocabulary². Figure 2 provides a more detailed graphical overview of the concepts and properties involved in the high-level description of an RO.

Figure 1: Research object model at a glance

² Web Annotation ontology: <https://www.w3.org/ns/oa>, and Web Annotation vocabulary: <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-vocab>

Figure 2. RO ontology overview

2.2 The EVER-EST RO Extensions

The Wf4Ever RO specification may be considered as the canonical specification for the representation of ROs in the literature, given that it was the first exhaustive and systematic representation of the RO concept after its inception. However, it was soon identified that it had to be adapted in order to support other research communities that were not so dependent on workflows. It also had to evolve considering the experience gathered with the initial implementation and deployment of research objects in practice.

The work done in the context of the EVER-EST project (<https://ever-est.eu/>) led into the extension of the Wf4Ever RO specification to support Earth Science-related research communities. This extension was led by RELIANCE partners PSNC and ESI. This work required extensive co-creation activities among knowledge representation experts involved in the creation of the original RO specification and members of those research communities. All the RO specification extensions were made available at <https://github.com/wf4ever/ro/tree/earth-science> and led into updates in some of the support tools, such as the ROHub portal (<http://www.rohub.org/>). ROHub portal was conceived as an evolution of the original Wf4Ever RO Portal.

The main extensions to the original RO specification, as discussed in EVER-EST’s deliverable D4.2 [3, 4], were the following:

- Creation of new vocabulary terms to describe geographic and time information associated to the resources aggregated in the Research Objects.
- Creation of new vocabulary terms to describe data access policies and intellectual property of the Research Object and of its aggregated resources.
- Generalization of concepts to cover not only scientific workflows but also other computational resources widely used in Earth Science disciplines.
- Extension of the list of RO types to characterize not only workflow-centric ROs, but also data-centric ROs, service-centric ROs, and documentation and bibliographic ROs.

Figure 4 RO evolution ontology overview

2.3 The RO-Crate Specification

The RO-Crate (Research Object Crate)³ specification is an ongoing effort that evolves the original Wf4Ever RO specification with a focus on simplicity and usability by non-Semantic Web experts. RO-Crate allows aggregating and describing the research artefacts used in the context of an investigation, including files and addressable resources (by means of URIs or other addressing schemes to locate digital or physical data). As with the previous models, both the artefacts and their metadata are included in the Research Object.

The main difference of this specification with respect to the previous ones is that it uses, by default, JSON-LD (a web developer-friendly serialization of RDF) and extends schema.org (a popular markup language for HTML pages) for those properties that are already defined in this general vocabulary. The main objective of such decision is to lower the entry barrier to adoption, making ROs more seamlessly integrated at a web scale and therefore discoverable through schema.org interoperability.

The structure followed by an RO-Crate is:

```
<RO-Crate root directory>/
| ro-crate-metadata.json # RO-Crate Metadata File MUST be present
| ro-crate-preview.html # RO-Crate Website homepage MAY be present
| ro-crate-preview_files/ # MAY be present
| | [other RO-Crate Website files]
| [payload files and directories] # 0 or more
```

³ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

The name of the RO-Crate root directory is not defined, but a root directory is identifiable by the presence of the RO-Crate Metadata File, with filename `ro-crate-metadata.json`. For instance, if an RO-Crate is archived in a ZIP-file, the ZIP root directory is an RO-Crate root directory if it contains the file `ro-crate-metadata.json`. Data Entities in the RO-Crate MUST either be payload files/directories present within the RO-Crate root directory or its subdirectories, or be Web-based Data Entities.

The RO-Crate JSON-LD context is defined in detail at: <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/1.1/appendix/jsonld.html>, and will be discussed further in the following sections.

RO-Crate is the latest trend and effort related to the representation of Research Objects, and consequently RELIANCE will adopt it as the main mechanisms to encode and expose its Research Objects.

3. Metadata models for the research artefacts included in ROs

This section provides a description of the general-purpose metadata models that are relevant for the representation of different entities that have been already identified as relevant for the RELIANCE ROs. This includes general-purpose metadata models that are used by RO-Crate, OpenAIRE and DataCite, the data cube metadata model that was described in deliverable D4.1 and other metadata models that can be used for the description of common types of entities that will be included in these ROs, such as software.

As a running example, we will use the following already-published and archived Research Object http://www.rohub.org/rodetails/InSAR_GPS_Campi_Flegrei_2011_2013-release/, which contains InSAR data and GPS data from INGV related to the Campi Flegrei caldera during 2011-2013. Whenever items that are not included in this RO need to be referred to, we will use other examples. A snapshot of the main page in ROHub for this Research Object is provided in Figure 4.

The screenshot shows the main description page of a Research Object (RO) in ROHub. The page title is "InSAR_GPS_Campi_Flegrei_2011_2013-release". At the top right, it shows a star rating of 5.00/5 (1 vote), 1 like, and 1 comment. Below the title, there are tabs for Overview, Content, Quality, Activity, Life cycle, Relations, and Impact. The Overview tab is active, showing various statistics: Views (3980), Downloads (20), Content (105), Activity (29), Forks (0), Snapshots (0), Quality (100), and Size (1.95 MB). The main content area includes the following fields:

- Research Area:** Geodesy
- Title:** InSAR and GPS data of the 2011-2013 unrest at Campi Flegrei (Italy)
- Description:** This Research Object contains the InSAR data (COSMO-SkyMed ascending and descending orbits) and GPS data from INGV related to the Campi Flegrei caldera during 2011-2013. The dataset was processed with GAMMA software and was subsampled with step 100m-150m. Ascii file and png images are stored.
- Link:** http://sandbox.rohub.org/rodl/ROs/InSAR_GPS_Campi_Flegrei_2011_2013-release/
- DOI:** 10.5072/ro-id.LZ743KUJ7Q
- Status:** ARCHIVE
- Creator:** Elisa Trasatti
- Creation date:** 26 February 2018, 15:49 (last modification: 28 November 2018, 06:44)
- Credits:** N/A [Elisa Trasatti]
- Research Object Type:** Data Research Object
- Purpose:** InSAR data
- Access level:** open
- Geolocation:** N/A
- Copyright holder:** IREAINGV_
- Sketch:** Two maps showing InSAR data. The left map is a topographic map of the Campi Flegrei caldera area, and the right map is a color-coded InSAR deformation map showing areas of uplift and subsidence.

Figure 5. Snapshot of the main description page of our sample Research Object archived in ROHub

3.1 General-purpose metadata models to describe ROs and their main associated entities

The RO-Crate specification proposes handling the Research Object as an entity (named *Root Data Entity*) together with a set of Contextual Entities for the representation of people, organisations, funders, etc. The *Root Data Entity* represents the Research Object itself (in terms of the folder structure it really represents the root folder) and MUST have the following properties:

- **@type:** MUST be Dataset
- **@id:** MUST end with / and SHOULD be the string ./
- **name:** SHOULD identify the dataset to humans well enough to disambiguate it from other RO-Crates
- **description:** SHOULD further elaborate on the name to provide a summary of the context in which the dataset is important.
- **datePublished:** MUST be a string in ISO 8601 date format and SHOULD be specified to at least the precision of a day, MAY be a timestamp down to the millisecond.
- **license:** SHOULD link to a *Contextual Entity* in the *RO-Crate Metadata File* with a name and description. MAY have a URI (e.g., for Creative Commons or Open Source licenses). MAY, if necessary be a textual description of how the RO-Crate may be used.

It must be noted that these properties are not enough to describe ROs according to DataCite, as required by OpenAIRE in its data provider guidelines (see D4.1). This is explicitly acknowledged in the RO-Crate specification and will be dealt with by the RO-Crate community in the future for a better integration with OpenAIRE. This may also lead to extensions in the RELIANCE-RO specification.

Next, we provide the RO-Crate general description based on the selected sample RO. The license is not completely specified in the original RO (it was claimed to be open) and a sample one has been selected. The name of this JSON-LD file is *ro-crate-metadata.json* and it MUST be located on the root folder of the RO-Crate.

```
{ "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "conformsTo": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1" },
      "about": { "@id": "." }
    },
    {
      "@id": "./",
      "identifier": "https://doi.org/10.5072/ro-id.LZ743KUH7Q",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "datePublished": "2018-02-26",
      "name": "InSAR and GPS data of the 2011-2013 unrest at Campi Flegrei (Italy) ",
      "description": " This Research Object contains the InSAR data (COSMO-Skymed ascending and descending orbits) and GPS data from INGV related to the Campi Flegrei caldera during 2011-2013.... ",
      "license": { "@id": " https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/" }
    },
    {
      "@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "description": "This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License",
      "identifier": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/",
      "name": "Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0)"
    }
  ]
}
```

According to the OpenAIRE metadata guidelines for data archives⁴, the following attributes would be covered by the previous description (in bold font those that are compulsory according to those guidelines):

- **Identifier** (identifier)
- **ResourceType** (resourceType equal to Dataset, for the time being, although we will aim at generating a ResearchObject resource type in the future, in collaboration with OpenAIRE).
- **Publication year** (publicationYear)
- **Title** (title)
- Description (descriptions/description)
- Rights List (rightsList/rights)

If we move into the *Contextual entities* that are also relevant for the RO-Crate, we can describe the following types of entities:

- People (connected to the RO via the `author` property)
- Organizations (connected to the RO via the `publisher` or `funder` property, or connected to a person via the `affiliation` property)
- Contact information (connected to a person or organization via the `contactPoint` property)
- Publications (connected to an RO via the `citation` property)
- Publisher (connected to an RO via the `publisher` property)
- Licensing, Access control and copyright (connected to an RO via the `license` property)

⁴ All the attributes presented in parenthesis in this general metadata layer belong to the DataCite metadata schema (<http://schema.datacite.org/>). Details on the usage of some of these properties can be also found, for the general metadata layer, at <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/>

-
- Subjects & keywords (represented as texts or resources, and connected to an RO via the `about` or `keywords` properties).
 - Thumbnails (connected to an RO as another data file, via `hasFile`, and with the property `thumbnail`)
 - Place (connected to an RO via the `contentLocation` property, and characterized with the `geo` property to provide specific coordinates)
 - Time (connected to an RO via the `temporalCoverage` property).

From these attributes, there are several that are also covered in the OpenAIRE guidelines, such as: **Authors** (creators/creator), **Contributors** (contributors/contributor), **Publisher** (publisher), **Funding References** (fundingReferences/fundingReference) and **Purpose** (subjects/subject, with free keywords). Authors and Publisher are compulsory in OpenAIRE, hence in bold font.

Finally, besides these attributes from the RO-Crate specification, other attributes that are not identified as compulsory according to the OpenAIRE guidelines but may be relevant as well are:

- Alternate identifier (`alternateIdentifiers/alternateIdentifier`)
- Related identifier (`relatedIdentifiers/relatedIdentifier`)
- Creation date (`dct:created`, `dates/date` [`dateType=`])
- Modification date (`dct:modified`)
- Publication date (`dct:date`)
- Version (`version`)
- Update frequency (`dct:accrualPeriodicity`)
- ParentIdentifier/inCollection (`eop:parentIdentifier`), where `eop` is the prefix for <http://www.opengis.net/eop/2.0>
- Status (`eop:status`)
- Language (`language`)
- Related Items (`relatedItems/relatedItem`)

3.2 General purpose models to describe Data Entities inside Research Objects

The Root Data Entity and the Contextual Entities that have been presented in the previous sections allow for the description of the RO as a whole, as well as the main entities that are normally associated to the RO or to many of its components (authors, funders, publications, etc.). However, one of the essential elements in an RO is the aggregation of other resources (datasets, software code, etc.). The RO-Crate specification identifies the possibility of including such resources by means of the so-called *Data Entities*⁵.

Data Entities can be Files, Directories or Web Resources, and they are referenced from an RO using the property `hasPart` from any element in the Research Object (e.g., from the Root Data Entity or from any other Data Entity, in a nested manner). The core metadata attributes to provide for any of these entities are the following:

- `@id`, to identify the data entity. It may be a relative URI to represent a path in the RO-Crate, or an absolute URI in case of a Web resource.
- `@type` to identify the type of data entity. It can be a single value (“File”, “Dataset”, “Workflow”) or an array of values (e.g., [“File”, “Workflow”]).

Besides these core metadata attributes, other commonly used attributes are:

- `name`
- `description`

⁵ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/1.1/data-entities.html>

- contentSize
- encodingFormat
- url
- distribution
- identifier (for any other type of identifier)

The following table summarises the main properties to use for describing any type of data entities inside Research Objects.

Note: In remainder of the document, we use the following prefixes:

- sch: as shortcut of the schema.org namespace (<http://schema.org/>)
- rel: as shortcut of the RELIANCE namespace (<http://w3id.org/earth-science/model#> - to be confirmed)

Table 1 Properties applicable to data entities inside Research Objects

RELIANCE-RO Term	Term type	Description
@id	data property	Identifier of the data entity
@type	object property	Type of data entity (e.g., File, Dataset, Workflow, etc.)
sch:name	data property	Name of the entity
sch:description	data property	Description of the entity
sch:contentSize	data property	Size of the content of the entity
sch:encodingFormat	data property	Encoding format used for the entity. It can be a string or a URL
sch:url	data property	URL with additional information about the entity
sch:distribution	object property	It leads to an entity of type sch:DataDownload
sch:identifier	object property	It leads to an entity of type sch:PropertyValue.

3.3 The Data Cube metadata model

The data cube metadata model proposed by RELIANCE was presented in deliverable D4.1. It is divided into four layers. Two of such layers represent general properties of the data cube and are already covered by the sets of attributes that have been presented in the previous two sections for general Data Entities. Hence in this section we focus on the new types of entities and attributes that we will deal with in the context of RELIANCE for the two additional layers. These will be further characterized in Section 4, when we describe more formally the RELIANCE RO-Crate application profile.

The first aspect that we need to consider is whether we want to add a new type of Dataset as the @type of a data cube. Our proposal, as discussed in Section 4, is to describe our datasets using an array that contains the type “File” (for compatibility with the original RO-Crate specification, and which may refer to a file inside the RO-Crate or to a reference to a Web resource – e.g., a call to a Data Cube API -) and one of the two new types “DataCubeCollection” or “DataCubeProduct”, which will be created by us.

The coverage metadata layer, as discussed in deliverable D4.1, contains a simple geolocation attribute for commonly used tools to allow displaying and searching for the regions that data cubes deal with,

as well as more specialized properties for the spatial, temporal and vertical coverages. The following attributes will be used in each case:

- **Simple geolocation and temporal coverage.** It will be represented as suggested in RO-Crate for Places and Times, with a Contextual Entity of type Place and a contextual entity of type Time, connected to the dataset via the `contentLocation` and `temporalCoverage` properties, respectively, from schema.org. For example:

```
{
  "@id": "https://sws.geonames.org/3176910/",
  "@type": "Place",
  "description": "The Campi Flegrei caldera is a large volcanic area situated to the west of Naples, Italy",
  "geo": {
    "@id": "#b4168a98-8534-4c6d-a568-64a55157b656",
    "@type": "GeoCoordinates",
    "latitude": "40.82316",
    "longitude": "14.19391",
    "name": "Latitude: 40.82316 Longitude: 14.19391"
  },
  "identifier": "http://sws.geonames.org/8152662/",
  "uri": "https://www.geonames.org/3176910 ",
  "name": "Campi Flegrei"
},
{
  "@id": "./Dataset/Data/obs_gps.dat",
  "@type": ["File", "DataCube"],
  "contentLocation": {
    "@id": "http://sws.geonames.org/3176910/"
  },
  "temporalCoverage": "2011/2013"
}
```

This is an example for a geographical item that is available in Geonames (Campi Flegrei) and that corresponds to a `sch:GeoCoordinates` point expressed as a latitude and longitude. Any other type of identifier (e.g., from Wikidata, internal identifier, a thesaurus or controlled lists of places used by a community) or geometry (described as a `sch:GeoCoordinates` or `sch:GeoShape`) would be valid. For the simple temporal coverage, it specifies that it refers to the period 2011-2013.

- **Spatial coverage.** This requires a more complex type of representation to describe the specific details of the spatial extent of the data cube (bounding boxes, polygons, multi polygons, line strings, etc.), the resolution of spatial steps in the observations made by an instrument and the coordinate reference system used. The following attributes will be included:
 - o **extent** (expressed as a WKT text)
 - o **spatial-step-resolution** (to describe the maximum level of resolution that has been used for observations)
 - o **coordinate-reference-system**
- **Temporal coverage.** Similarly, this is a more complex type of representation for which we propose a RELIANCE extension as it is not covered in schema.org.
 - o **sch:startTime** (expressed as ISO8601)
 - o **sch:endTime** (expressed as ISO8601)
 - o **temporal-step-resolution** (to describe the maximum level of temporal resolution that has been used for observations)
 - o **temporal-reference-system**
- **Vertical coverage.** This is relevant for aspects related to the elevation of places for which data cubes contain observations or the depth in the case of water bodies like seas, oceans, etc. Similarly, this is proposed as a RELIANCE extension:

- **highestElevation**
- **lowestElevation**
- **vertical-step-resolution**
- **vertical-reference-system**

The last layer where we may need to add additional metadata for in our data cubes is the data acquisition and product information layer, as described in deliverable D4.1. This layer contains several attributes that are covered in the RO-Crate specification (and in schema.org), such as:

- sch:keywords (already discussed in the general layer for RO-Crate)
- sch:contentSize
- sch:encodingFormat
- sch:contactPoint

And other attributes that have been created by us in our RELIANCE extension are:

- product type
- product version
- data type
- data type unit
- processing level
- processor
- instrument
- platform
- other Data Acquisition System
- data Quality
- maxValue
- minValue
- noDataValue
- links to resources

The following table provides a summary of all these properties:

Table 2 Properties applicable to data cube data entities inside Research Objects

RELIANCE-RO Term	Term type	Description
@id	data property	
@type	object property	Array containing “File” and one of the following: DataCubeCollection, DataCubeProduct
sch:contentLocation	object property	Simple link to an entity that describes the location for this data cube
sch:temporalCoverage	data property	Simple description of the temporal coverage (e.g., 2011/2013)
rel:extent	data property	WKT description of the spatial object
rel:spatialStepResolution	data property	Resolution of observations
rel:coordinateReferenceSystem	data property	Coordinate reference system used for the WKT coordinates

sch:startTime	data property	Start time for the temporal coverage
sch:endTime	data property	End time for the temporal coverage
rel:temporalStepResolution	data property	Resolution (temporal) of the observations
rel:temporalReferenceSystem	data property	Temporal reference system, if different from the usual one
rel:highestElevation	data property	Value of the highest elevation
rel:lowestElevation	data property	Value of the lowest elevation
rel:verticalStepResolution	data property	Resolution (vertical) of the observations
rel:verticalReferenceSystem	data property	Vertical reference system, if different from the usual one (e.g., meters)
sch:keywords	data property	Keywords
sch:contentSize	data property	Size of the content of the entity
sch:encodingFormat	data property	Encoding format used for the entity. It can be a string or a URL
sch:contactPoint	object property	Link to an entity that acts as contact point for this data cube
rel:productType	data property	Type of product or collection
rel:productVersion	data property	Version of the product or collection
rel:dataType	data property	Type of the data for observations
rel:dataTypeUnit	data property	Unit for observations
rel:processingLevel	data property	Processing level
rel:processor	property	It may be a string or the id of the processor
rel:instrument	property	Same as above
rel:platform	property	Same as above
rel:otherDataAcquisitionSystem	property	Same as above
rel:dataQuality	data property	Any detail on the quality of data
rel:maxValue	data property	Maximum value for the observations
rel:minValue	data property	Minimum value for the observations
rel:noDataValue	data property	Value used in case that no data is available, as a way to represent null
rel:linksToResources	object property	Links to other relevant resources

3.4 Software description metadata models

Software is a crucial asset for understanding and reusing existing research artefacts. Hence, the scientific community has developed vocabularies to describe research software at different levels of granularity. We describe the most relevant efforts below, highlighting the properties and concepts from those with most reuse potential for ROs. At this stage we have not decided on which specific metadata model to use for this purpose, as this is research in progress in EOSC and RDA.

CodeMeta and Schema.org. Schema.org has been widely used to describe individual research artefacts such as datasets, but also includes properties to describe software applications and source code. Some of the most relevant properties for **source code** include:

- `codeRepository`: URL of the code repository where a software component is stored
- `programmingLanguage`: language used in the code
- `runtimePlatform`: platform used to run a software component
- `targetApplication`: software application built from the code.

Other relevant but more generic metadata (authors, publisher, licence, keywords, etc.) are shared with other artefacts such as datasets. Some of the most relevant properties for **software applications** include:

- `applicationCategory`: type of software application, such as “Game”
- `downloadURL`: URL where the software application can be downloaded
- `installURL`: link to the instructions of the software application
- `operatingSystem`: OS used to run the software application
- `memoryRequirements`: minimum memory requirements needed to deploy the software application
- `preprocessorRequirements`: minimum processor requirements needed to deploy the software application
- `softwareHelp`: link to the manual of the software application
- `softwareVersion`: version number used to identify this software application release.

CodeMeta (<https://codemeta.github.io/terms/>) expands Schema.org by including additional properties relevant in research software projects, such as the reference publication of a software application, who the maintainer is, how to build a software component or funding information.

EDAM. Ontology for bioscientific data analysis, used in Bioinformatics (e.g., by Biotoools <https://bio.tools/>). EDAM (<http://edamontology.org>) includes a generic way for describing operations (defined as “functions that process a set of inputs and results in a set of outputs”), their inputs, outputs and formats; as well as a categorization of the different types of tasks common to bioscientific analyses.

Software Ontology (SWO). Extension of the EDAM ontology to describe software metadata. SWO (<http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/swo.owl>) also extends the Basic Formal Ontology and the Relations Ontology to describe software relationships. SWO describes a thorough taxonomy of programming languages, licenses and algorithms, but defines them as classes instead of instances, adding an additional level of complexity when operating with the ontology.

Description of a Project Ontology (DOAP). The DOAP ontology (<http://usefulinc.com/ns/doap#>) focuses on describing the roles associated with the participants of a research project. The metadata and roles used for this purpose overlap with the roles and descriptions in research software projects.

Software Description Ontology (SD). Ontology extending Schema.org and Codemeta to represent research software, its inputs, outputs and variables. In particular, SD introduces concepts to link software versions and configurations defining partial parameter values and their constraints [6]. In addition, SD allows describing the dataset variables associated with inputs and outputs types.

Core Software Ontology (CSO). Together with the Core Ontology of Software Components (COSC), CSO (<http://km.aifb.kit.edu/sites/cos/>) extends the DOLCE upper ontology [7] to describe software libraries and web services. CSO specifies concepts related to software and data, and includes both software components and services. COSC extends CSO to define software components further. An

interesting aspect of these ontologies is that inputs and outputs of software are defined as roles, played by different types of data. Roles are adopted for addressing policies, which have to be specified by users. These formalizations require users to understand logic inference in ways that makes the vocabularies difficult to reuse. The link between software inputs and their expected contents is not modeled in CSO.

Workflow Infrastructure Conservation Using Semantics (WICUS). The WICUS ontology network [8] is a set of ontologies designed to represent the information about the computational infrastructure involved on the execution of computational scientific experiments (including memory, processor and other hardware requirements). This ontology was designed for scientific workflows, but many of its concepts and properties can be reused for research software.

4. Data Cube-centric Research Objects in RELIANCE

A Data Cube-centric Research Object is a Research Object that aggregates at least one Data Cube. It MAY aggregate any other kind of resources, but MUST aggregate at least one Data Cube.

A Data Cube-centric RO treats Data Cubes as first-class resources, which are aggregated and described in detail with information such as how it was generated (specification) or used. A Data Cube includes metadata like identification, description, resolution as well as the particular parameters used to generate the dataset or subset and the link for access. This particular metadata is described in detail in D4.1. A Data Cube is identified and aggregated in an RO through its identifier. The identifier will be generally a link pointing to a Data Cube in a Web Service (e.g., https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/datasets?datasetId=MXD11_L2_Emis31)

Additionally, the Data Cube-centric RO, MAY include other related resources like:

- Jupyter Notebook (link to the notebook) that is using this Data Cube via the ADAM API,
- Intermediate and final results from the analysis of the data (link to the data in some repository, e.g., B2Share or Zenodo)
- Related documentation
- Related publications

4.1 The RELIANCE RO-Crate application profile

Taking into account the possibility of creating application profiles for RO-Crate⁶, this section provides a description of the main characteristics of an RO-Crate application profile that would provide support for the types of Research Objects that will be handled in RELIANCE.

First of all, the whole Research Object MUST be represented with the following structure:

```
<RO-Crate root directory>/
| ro-crate-metadata.json # RO-Crate Metadata File MUST be present
| ro-crate-preview.html # RO-Crate Website homepage MAY be present
| ro-crate-preview_files/ # MAY be present
| | [other RO-Crate Website files]
| [payload files and directories] # 0 or more
```

All these files will follow the recommendations that have been already identified in RO-Crate for each of the entities (Root Data Entity, Data Entities and Contextual Entities).

⁶ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/profiles.html>

A valid RO-Crate JSON-LD graph MUST describe:

- The RO-Crate Metadata File Descriptor (see Section 2.2.1 for an example)
- The Root Data Entity (see Section 2.2.1 for an example)
- Zero or more Data Entities
- Zero or more Contextual Entities

The RO-Crate Metadata File Descriptor and Root Data Entity have already been described in Section 2.2.1, and hence we will not provide more details here. We will now focus on the specific Data Entities that are specialisations of those in the general RO-Crate profile, such as those for the data cubes and those for software.

A RELIANCE RO-Crate MAY include at least one Data Cube Data Entity, which MUST have the following properties:

- `@type`: MUST be `DataCubeCollection` or `DataCubeProduct`.
- `@id`: MUST be either a URI Path relative to the RO Crate root, or an absolute URI, which can point to a file with the data cube or to a Web service call that allows generating the data cube on demand.

A Data Cube Data Entity MAY include the following properties:

- `@contentLocation`: MUST be the id of a Contextual Entity of type `Place`.
- `@temporalCoverage`: MUST be a temporal range specified as a period (e.g., 2011/2013).

A Data Cube Data Entity MUST include the following properties:

- `@rel:spatialCoverage`: MUST be the id of a Contextual Entity that identifies the spatial coverage in detail, including `rel:extent` (expressed as a WKT text), `rel:spatial-step-resolution` and `rel:coordinate-reference-system`.
- `@rel:temporalCoverage`: MUST be the id of a Contextual Entity that identifies the temporal coverage in detail, including `rel:beginningTime` (expressed as ISO8601), `rel:endTime` (expressed as ISO8601), `rel:temporal-step-resolution` and `rel:temporal-reference-system-unit`.

A Data Cube Data Entity MAY include the following property:

- `@verticalCoverage`: MUST be the id of a Contextual Entity that identifies the vertical coverage in detail, including `rel:highestValue`, `rel:lowestValue`, `rel:vertical-step-resolution` and `rel:vertical-reference-system-unit`.

A Data Cube Data Entity SHOULD include the properties:

- `sch:name`
- `sch:description`
- `sch:keywords` (already discussed in the general layer for RO-Crate)
- `sch:contentSize`
- `sch:encodingFormat`
- `sch:contactPoint`

A Data Cube Data Entity MAY include the properties:

- `rel:product-type`
- `rel:product-version`
- `rel:data-type`
- `rel:data-type-unit`
- `rel:processing-level`

-
- rel:processor
 - rel:instrument
 - rel:platform
 - rel:other-data-acquisition-system
 - rel:dataquality
 - rel:maxValue
 - rel:minValue
 - rel:maxDate
 - rel:minDate
 - rel:noDataValue
 - rel:links-to-resources

In what relates to the software description, the following will be included as a Data Entity. A RELIANCE RO-Crate MAY include one or more Software Data Entities, which MUST have the following properties:

- @type: MUST be Software.
- @id: MUST be either a URI Path relative to the RO Crate root, or an absolute URI, which can point to a file with the software, to a DOI with the software or to a Web address of the repository of the software.

A Software Data Entity SHOULD include the following properties (besides the Data Cube Entity properties):

- sch:name
- sch:description
- sch:license
- sch:softwareVersion
- sch:author
- sch:codeRepository
- cm:referencePublication

A Software Data Entity MAY include the following properties:

- cm:buildInstructions
- sch:programmingLanguage
- sch:runtimePlatform
- sch:downloadURL
- sch:operatingSystem
- sch:memoryRequirements
- sch:preprocessorRequirements
- sch:publisher
- cm:readme

Finally, in terms of the evolution of RELIANCE ROs, the following elements are to be considered in our profile:

A RELIANCE RO-Crate MAY include the following properties (from the RO-Evo ontology):

- roevo:archivedAtTime, which represents the release date of the Research Object.
- roevo:snapshottedAtTime, which represents the snapshot date of the Research Object.
- eop:status, which MUST have any of the following values: liveRO, forkedRO, snapshotRO or archivedRO.
- roevo:wasArchivedBy, which MUST point to a Contextual Entity of type Person.
- roevo:wasSnapshottedBy, which MUST point to a Contextual Entity of type Person.

Other properties from the RO-Evo ontology MAY be also included, following that ontology.

4.2 Implementation of the RELIANCE RO-Crate in ROHub

As previously mentioned, ROHub is the one of the RELIANCE services that will be integrated in EOSC and made available via the EOSC portal and marketplace.

ROHub is nowadays the reference platform for research object management, supporting the preservation and lifecycle management of scientific investigations, research campaigns and operational processes. As the only existing platform implementing natively the full Research Object model and paradigm, resources associated with a particular experiment are aggregated in a single digital entity (Research Object), and metadata relevant to understand and interpret the content is represented as semantic annotations that are user and machine readable. ROHub constitutes the backbone to a wealth of RO-centric applications and interfaces across different scientific communities.

ROHub comprises a backend service (RODL), exposing a set of Restful APIs, a reference web client application (ROHub portal), and integrates multiple added-value research object services, as described in Deliverable D6.1.

As RELIANCE will use RO-Crate as the main mechanisms to encode and expose Research Objects, ROHub will be adapted to be able to import and export RO-Crate(s) with the RELIANCE extensions. As a first step in this direction, it is necessary to establish mappings between the terms in the EVER-EST RO model (which extends the original RO model) that ROHub currently implements, to terms in RO-Crate. This meant mostly mappings to schema.org, although few terms from other vocabularies are used in RO-Crate including terms of the original RO model.

The table below shows the result of the initial mapping exercise.

Table 3 Mapping between EVER-EST RO specification terms and RO Crate terms

EVER-EST RO term	term type	RO-Crate term
http://purl.org/dc/terms/audience	object property	http://schema.org/audience
http://purl.org/dc/terms/contributor	object property	http://schema.org/contributor
http://purl.org/dc/terms/creator	object property	http://schema.org/creator
http://purl.org/dc/terms/format	object property	http://schema.org/encodingFormat
http://purl.org/dc/terms/hasPart	object property	http://schema.org/hasPart
http://purl.org/dc/terms/isPartOf	object property	http://schema.org/isPartOf
http://purl.org/dc/terms/license	object property	http://schema.org/license
http://purl.org/dc/terms/publisher	object property	http://schema.org/publisher
http://purl.org/dc/terms/subject	object property	http://schema.org/about
http://purl.org/pav/authoredBy	object property	https://schema.org/author
http://purl.org/pav/contributedBy	object property	http://schema.org/contributor
http://purl.org/pav/createdBy	object property	http://schema.org/creator
http://purl.org/wf4ever/roevo#relatedResource	object property	http://schema.org/isRelatedTo
http://purl.org/wf4ever/roterms#defaultValue	object property	https://schema.org/defaultValue

http://purl.org/wf4ever/roterms#requiresSoftware	object property	http://schema.org/softwareRequirements
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wfdesc#hasInput	object property	https://w3id.org/cwl/cwl#inputs
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wfdesc#hasOutput	object property	https://w3id.org/cwl/cwl#outputs
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wfdesc#hasSource	object property	https://w3id.org/cwl/cwl#source
http://schema.theodi.org/odrs#copyrightHolder	object property	http://schema.org/copyrightHolder
http://www.openarchives.org/ore/terms/similarTo	object property	http://schema.org/isSimilarTo
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#agent	object property	http://schema.org/agent
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#atLocation	object property	https://schema.org/location
http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/fundedBy	object property	http://schema.org/funder
http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/thumbnail	object property	http://schema.org/thumbnail
http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type	object property	@type (JSON-LD)
http://dbpedia.org/ontology/fileSize	data property	http://schema.org/fileSize
http://purl.org/dc/terms/created	data property	http://schema.org/dateCreated
http://purl.org/dc/terms/description	data property	http://schema.org/description
http://purl.org/dc/terms/identifier	data property	http://schema.org/identifier
http://purl.org/dc/terms/issued	data property	http://schema.org/dateIssued
http://purl.org/dc/terms/modified	data property	http://schema.org/dateModified
http://purl.org/dc/terms/title	data property	http://schema.org/title
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wf4ever#filePath	data property	http://schema.org/contentUrl
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wf4ever#serviceURL	data property	http://schema.org/serviceUrl
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wfprov#durationInSeconds	data property	http://schema.org/duration
http://schema.theodi.org/odrs#copyrightYear	data property	http://schema.org/copyrightYear
http://swrc.ontoware.org/ontology#keywords	data property	http://schema.org/keywords
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#endedAtTime	data property	http://schema.org/endTime
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#startedAtTime	data property	http://schema.org/startTime
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#value	data property	http://schema.org/value
http://purl.org/dc/terms/abstract	data property	http://schema.org/abstract
http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/name	data property	http://schema.org/name
http://purl.org/co/Collection	class	https://schema.org/Collection
http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/Collection	class	https://schema.org/Collection
http://purl.org/wf4ever/roterms#Paper	class	https://schema.org/Article
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wf4ever#Dataset	class	http://schema.org/Dataset
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wf4ever#Document	class	http://schema.org/DigitalDocument
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wf4ever#File	class	http://schema.org/MediaObject
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wf4ever#Image	class	http://schema.org/ImageObject
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wf4ever#WebService	class	https://schema.org/WebAPI

http://purl.org/wf4ever/wfdesc#Input	class	https://w3id.org/cwl/cwl#InputParameter
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wfdesc#Output	class	https://w3id.org/cwl/cwl#OutputParameter
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wfdesc#Parameter	class	https://w3id.org/cwl/cwl#Parameter
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wfdesc#Process	class	https://w3id.org/cwl/cwl#Process
http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#Thing	class	http://schema.org/Thing
http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#Dataset	class	http://schema.org/Dataset
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#Organization	class	http://schema.org/Organization
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#Person	class	http://schema.org/Person
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#Plan	class	https://schema.org/PlanAction
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#Quotation	class	https://schema.org/Quotation
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#Role	class	http://schema.org/Role
http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/Person	class	http://schema.org/Person
http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/Project	class	http://schema.org/Project
http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/Organization	class	http://schema.org/Organization
http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/contributor	annotation property	http://schema.org/contributor
http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/creator	annotation property	http://schema.org/creator
http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/description	annotation property	http://schema.org/description
http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/title	annotation property	http://schema.org/title
http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#comment	annotation property	http://schema.org/comment
http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#versionInfo	annotation property	http://schema.org/version
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#category	annotation property	http://schema.org/category
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#inverse	annotation property	http://schema.org/inverseOf
http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1#identifier	annotation property	http://schema.org/identifier

5. Conclusions and next steps

This deliverable has presented how the RO concept can be applied in the context of the research communities addressed by RELIANCE. In our work, we have reviewed several implementations for the RO concept that have been proposed over time (the seminal Wf4Ever RO specification and its extension for Earth Science in the EVER-EST project, and the ongoing RO-Crate specification). After this analysis, we have determined the relevance and cost of opportunity of contributing a specific application profile focused on Earth Sciences for RO-Crate, so as to provide support for the representation of the Research Objects that will be handled by the research communities that participate in RELIANCE, as well as to drive the support that the ROHub system will provide for the creation and management of Research Objects.

We expect that the implementation of this application profile in ROHub, as well as the modifications that some of the models that are being reused or that the model is inspired by, such as the RO-Crate, the OpenAire metadata guidelines, the software metadata models, etc., will lead into changes in this specification, which will be maintained live in the corresponding GitHub repository of the project.

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